

STANDARD OPERATIONAL PROCESSES IN PHARMACIES

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Relevance: Creating a quality system requires the development of standard operational procedures for the sale of medicinal products and pharmacy assortment goods, as well as for all types of work that influence the quality of activities.

Objective of the research: To analyze the implementation of standard operational processes to regulate all pharmacy processes in accordance with O'zMSSt 140:2024 requirements.

Methods and techniques: The standard operational processes developed based on survey and internal audit results will be studied for their application in the practice of chain pharmacies "Yangiqorqhon Drug-Pharmacy" LLC.

When introducing the latest information technology systems to carry out pharmacy functions sequentially, document reconciliation and decision-making do not become faster, leading to increased costs. This often makes it difficult to achieve the expected economic benefits. Currently, the components performing specific functions in pharmacies are viewed as inefficient, closed systems. In this approach, consumer interests are neglected, and the overall impact on pharmacy operations is minimal.

Moreover, the lack of formal documentation of processes and the unclear division of responsibilities complicate adaptive management. The absence of clear regulation of individual functions not only reduces the quality of products and services but also leads to inefficient resource allocation and lower profitability of pharmacies.

Results: Based on surveys, regardless of ownership form and structure (chain pharmacies, individual pharmacies, social pharmacies, internal pharmacies located in treatment and prophylactic institutions), the main departments with almost all pharmacy functions were identified. Furthermore, 85.0% of chain pharmacies combined non-prescription and prescription departments, while 60.0% of individual pharmacies had them as independent departments. When analyzing the procurement of goods, it was found that in 60.0% of pharmacy networks, they could not independently purchase assortment goods, while in 30.0%, this was possible only in specific cases, and in 10.0%, only for hygienic products. The procurement of the same product from different suppliers by pharmacies (both chain and individual) indicates the absence of a unified approach to pricing, which results in price variations.

Conclusion: Standard operational processes improve clarity of pharmacy functions, minimize errors, ensure transparency in drug control, enable sales under clear supervision, and enhance the safety of pharmaceutical activities. This increases operational efficiency, reduces the risk of errors and financial losses, and guarantees compliance with the GPP national standards and legal requirements.